

POST-20cl

POST-20cl #1

Possible ALL #38, dist = 10.87

Possible ALL #37, dist = 17.01

Possible ALL #14, dist = 25.57

POST-20cl #2

Possible ALL #14, dist = 13.76

Possible ALL #37, dist = 14.65

Possible ALL #38, dist = 22.75

POST-20cl #3

Possible ALL #40, dist = 5.65

Possible ALL #39, dist = 55.57

Possible ALL #12, dist = 77.42

POST-20cl #4

Possible ALL #31, dist = 24.1

Possible ALL #14, dist = 35.7

Possible ALL #15, dist = 36.06

POST-20cl #5

Possible ALL #37, dist = 20.07

Possible ALL #14, dist = 22.18

Possible ALL #38, dist = 24.88

POST-20cl #6

Possible ALL #32, dist = 12.08

Possible ALL #13, dist = 15.91

Possible ALL #24, dist = 18.7

POST-20cl #7

Possible ALL #15, dist = 16.12

Possible ALL #13, dist = 25.05

Possible ALL #24, dist = 28.01

POST-20cl #8

Possible ALL #12, dist = 25.45

Possible ALL #17, dist = 43.84

Possible ALL #39, dist = 48.83

POST-20cl #9

Possible ALL #35, dist = 25.26

Possible ALL #15, dist = 41.47

Possible ALL #14, dist = 45.01

POST-20cl #10

Possible ALL #13, dist = 20.04

Possible ALL #34, dist = 21.72

Possible ALL #11, dist = 25.6

POST-20cl #11

Possible ALL #34, dist = 18.13

Possible ALL #32, dist = 20.46

Possible ALL #13, dist = 20.9

POST-20cl #12

Possible ALL #15, dist = 27.4

Possible ALL #13, dist = 36.31

Possible ALL #32, dist = 39.97

POST-20cl #13

Possible ALL #21, dist = 22.33

Possible ALL #20, dist = 36.37

Possible ALL #33, dist = 42.53

POST-20cl #14

Possible ALL #20, dist = 26.06

Possible ALL #21, dist = 40.24

Possible ALL #33, dist = 48.83

POST-20cl #15

Possible ALL #24, dist = 16.63

Possible ALL #25, dist = 21.08

Possible ALL #23, dist = 24.71

POST-20cl #16

Possible ALL #32, dist = 12.95

Possible ALL #34, dist = 24.82

Possible ALL #24, dist = 29.11

POST-20cl #17

Possible ALL #25, dist = 18

Possible ALL #26, dist = 19.77

Possible ALL #24, dist = 22.44

POST-20cl #18

Possible ALL #26, dist = 16.92

Possible ALL #13, dist = 24.01

Possible ALL #34, dist = 26.15

POST-20cl #19

Possible ALL #19, dist = 31.44

Possible ALL #9, dist = 32.51

Possible ALL #15, dist = 35.55

POST-20cl #20

Possible ALL #17, dist = 30.3

Possible ALL #19, dist = 35.59

Possible ALL #9, dist = 43.56